

The Perception Of Guidance Counsellors By Nigerian Secondary Schools Principals Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the perception of Guidance Counsellors by Bayelsa State principals in Yenagoa Local Government Area. The design for the study is descriptive survey. The population is made up of all principals in Yenagoa Local Government Area, they are forty-six in number (46), (Bayelsa State Schools Board Planning, Research and Statistics Department). A questionnaire titled Principals perception of counselling Inventory (PPCL) was of ten (10) items with a reliability coefficient of 0.74. This was administered to principals of the various schools in the local government. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions 1 and 2 while test was used to analyze the research question 3. The research revealed that though principals support the idea of Counsellors employment in Schools, their perceptions of who and the duties of a Counsellor is still very wrong. For instances they feel a Counsellor can take the role of an absent teacher, any other teacher can do the work of a School Counsellor or the work of a school disciplinarian etc. There was no gender difference in principals' perception of Counsellors. It was also recommended amidst others that counsellors should be fully employed in Schools and that principals, staff and students should be given proper orientation of the Counsellor and his functions.

Keywords: Perception, Guidance Counsellor and Principals

INTRODUCTION

The Concept of Guidance and Counselling:

Omoni (2009) in Yunusa (2018) describes Counselling as a process in which one specialist called Counsellor assists others called clients in a face to face interaction to solve a dynamic problem and deal with a situation and make wise and intelligent choice and decision. Bobga and Nahanum (2016) define Guidance and Counselling as a service (within and outside the school setting) that helps people understand themselves, provided the client reveals accurate reliable and valid information about him or herself and his/her environment. Mallam, (2000) in Yunusa (2018) asserts that counselling is the process which occurs in a one on one relationship between an individual with problems he cannot cope with and a professional worker qualified to help him and others in solving their problems. Kolo (2012) is of the opinion that Counselling is the relationship that is qualitative enough to change or affect people positively.

Thus, Guidance Counselling can be described as a process where a professional Counsellor, who is a Guidance Counsellor assists a client(s) to identify his / her problem(s) and also enables such to solve his / her problem (s) Guidance and Counselling is characterized by mutual respect, effective communication, genuine and complete acceptances of the client, concentration on the needs, problems and feeling of the

client (empathy) with the intention of providing meaningful solutions. (Egbo 2015). Chibudu and Echebe (2009) in Onomuodeke and Iruluh (2011) highlights the characteristic of counselling as confidentiality, empathy, sincerity, integrity, resistance, respect etc. The service rendered by the Guidance and Counsellors are as follows: Orientation services, information services, Counselling services, Appraised services, placement services, referral services, follow up services etc. Enekeme and Torubeli (2017) and Gidimi, Yinwa, Adebayo, Kulubu (2020) and Njoku and Ugwegbulam (2015)

In view of the prevalent problems ranging from educational, vocational, personal, social problems that is prevalent in our society and especially in our schools, the importance of Guidance and Counselling in our schools' settings cannot be over emphasized. Guidance and Counselling as an academic discipline actually started in United State of America (USA) at the beginning of the 20th century with emphasis on vocational Guidance. It is on the same treads that it is spill over to Nigeria and other countries of the world (Akpan 2018). In Nigeria the formal Guidance and Counselling started in Nigeria in (1959) by a group of Catholic Irish Reverend Sisters at saint Theresa College Oke-Ado in Ibadan. It gradually moved from one level to the other by some distinguished personalities like Professor Olu Makinde, professor Adebayo Gesinde, professor M. Para Allumu, Dr (Mrs) Christies C. Achebe, Professor Christiopher, G. M Bakare, Professor Frank C. Carew, Professor Adeyem Idowu, Professor Okobia amongst a host of others. These individuals have worked tirelessly to ensure that Guidance and Counselling is well grounded in this country. Also because of its valuable and striking benefits it offers, the Federal Government in 1977 included Guidance and Counselling in the National Policy on Educational Institutions (Ikejiaku & Torubeli 2010).

From the foregoing and the injunction that has been given by the federal government of Nigeria to implement Guidance and Counselling due to the varied and numerous advantages that is quite overwhelming, there is the need for every school and every State to employ its services (Ikejiaku & Torubeli 2010).

However, it has been observed that some states have not been able to adhere to the injunction of the Federal Government by employing Counsellors who can render Guidance and Counselling Services in schools Agbakwuru in Njoku and Ugwugbulam (2015) opined that the school administrator sees the Counsellor as a rival. Most principals do not perceive any difference between them and school counsellors. They believe that they are capable and have been carrying out Guidance Services very successfully in schools before the introduction of formal Guidance and Counselling in schools Ikeme and Nwoye (1988) in Arowolo (2013) discovered that when counsellors are posted to schools. Principals assign duties to them according to their school need. Most of the times, the counsellors may be asked to play the role of vice principal, subject teachers, labour master or school clerk.

Yusuf, Zahyah, Lasis, Adekola and Famola (2021) carried out a research on principals' perception of Guidance and Counselling services in Kwara State Secondary Schools. Nigeria, implication for stakeholders. They discovered that principals believed the provision of counselling services had a significant impact on student's academic achievement. Even through most of the Secondary Schools do not have a good counselling unit. Qualified Counsellors and Counselling facilities. From the above, it can be deduced that there is missing link that should be filled. Guidance and Counselling services are quite enormous and beneficial to the growth and development of any people or nation. Its efficacy cannot just be ignored especially in our institute of learning where our young ones are seriously faced with all sort of academic, vocational and personal social problems. It is quite expedient to include it in our school curriculum in order to prevent impending problems and solve existing ones.

Statement of the Problem

Human beings are always faced with myriads of problems that poses a threat to their growth and development in life. When such life threatening situations are met with adequate and appropriate solutions, life becomes more satisfying and fulfilling. Guidance and Counselling can provide services that can make an individual live a well-adjusted and meaningful life. Counselling is also designed to perform vital roles in preventing educational, personal, social, mental, emotional, and other similar problems among the

undergraduate students (Makinde 2015). In other to overcome all forms of life inadequacies, Guidance and counselling provides appropriate assistance to students to better understanding and accept themselves, their personalities, endowment, their strength and weakness, their attitudes and worth as unique individuals. These are the fundamental reasons for the introduction of Guidance and Counseling Services in our schools (Arowolo 2013). He also noted other behavioural problems such as cultism, truancy, examination Malpractice and bullying. Thus, if these are not properly handled, there may be problems of Low achievers, under achievers or complete failures etc. When they are completely frustrated because of lack of proper counselling they may drop out of school. This may eventually degenerate to the high rate of crime, such as robbery, drug addiction, banditry, prostitution, kidnapping, cybercrime etc.

Thus, a state where Guidance and Counselling is not operational in schools there is the tendency that such social vices may thrive. It is based on this premise that the researcher has decided to carry out this study to examine the perception of principals of Guidance and Counselling Services in schools. The paper decided to narrow it down to the principals because some authors has attributed some problems to them. The researcher also decided to find out if it is the same with Bayelsa State, and also most States in Nigeria have Guidance Counsellors in their State. (Ikejiaku & Torubeli 2010). The researcher is also worried that it is not in Bayelsa Public Schools, thus, the researcher is handling Yenagoa Local Government Area first.

Purpose of Study

1. To find out how many schools in Yenagoa local government area of Bayelsa state have Guidance Counselors.
2. To investigate the perception of principals towards counsellors in schools.
3. To ascertain whether there will be gender difference of Principals perception towards Counsellors in Schools.

Research Questions.

1. How many schools have functional Guidance Counsellors?
2. What is the perception of principals towards Counsellors in schools?
3. What is the perception of principals towards Counsellors based on gender?

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

The description survey design was used in the study.

Population

The population of the study comprises of all principals in all the public secondary schools in Yenagoa local government area of Bayelsa state. There are forty-six of them.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The Census Survey technique was used. Census Survey involves studying all elements of a population. Conditions for census survey is when the population is small, when there is ample time available for the project research Offor, (2022).

Instruments

The instruments for data's collection in the research work was a questionnaire titled Principals' Perception of Counselling Inventory (PPCI). It was a ten item inventory. There was also a yes or no question to get information as to whether the schools have Counsellors in their school. The remaining ten (10) questions were aimed at soliciting information about the Perception of Counsellors by Principals. The PPCL was a four-point likert type questionnaire designed by the researcher to determine the response levels with the items through the following response options and were weighed as follows: SA (Strongly Agree, 4); A (Agree, 3); DA (Disagree, 2); and SD (strongly disagree, 1). Face validity was done by experts in measurement and evaluation in Niger Delta University. The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was 0.74. The test – retest reliability method was used. The instrument was administered to the forty-six (46) principals in Yenagoa Local Government Area. The mean and standard Deviation was used to answer question 1 and 2, while question 3 was analyzed with T test. The criterion mean was 2.50 to

analyze the research question. Any response below 2.50 shows that they don't know what Guidance, Counselling is all about, or who a Guidance counsellor is.

DATA ANALYSIS

The findings of the research are based on research question

Research Question 1: *How many schools have functional Guidance Counsellor?*

Table 1: Percentage of Guidance Counsellor in Schools.

Do you have a functional Guidance Counsellor in your school? Yes or No.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	12	46%
Disagree	34	74%
Total	46	100%

Research Question 2. *What is the perception of principals towards counsellors in School?*

Table 2: Perception of Principals towards Counsellors in Schools.

S/N		SA	A	D	CS	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	I don't really understand the function of a Guidance Counsellor in School	15 (60)	5 (15)	7 (14)	19 (19)	2.34	1.32	Disagreed
2.	I feel a Guidance Counsellor can perform any role in the school	2 (8)	9 (27)	15 (30)	20 (20)	1.84	0.89	Disagreed
3.	A Guidance Counsellor can perform the role of a school disciplinarian	15 (60)	12 (36)	15 (30)	4 (4)	2.82	0.99	Agreed
4.	I see the counsellor as one that can take the class of an absent teacher	15 (60)	24 (72)	6 (12)	1 (1)	3.15	0.72	Agreed
5.	Any other teacher can do the work of a Guidance counsellor	2 (8)	12 (36)	20 (40)	12 (12)	2.60	0.77	Agreed
6.	The school counsellor can handle disciplinary position in the school	14 (56)	26 (78)	6 (12)	-	3.17	0.64	Agreed
7.	The school counselor be employed but funding, may be a problem	12 (48)	18 (54)	10 (20)	6 (6)	2.78	0.96	Agreed
8.	They can help in sorting out educational vocational and person social problem in school	19 (76)	19 (57)	6 (2)	2 (2)	3.19	0.83	Agreed
9.	I do not support their employment in schools	1 (4)	3 (9)	12 (24)	30 (30)	1.45	0.72	Disagreed
10.	Even when they are employed there is no office for them in the school.	5 (20)	23 (69)	12 (24)	6 (6)	2.58	0.85	Agreed

Research Question 3: *What is the perception of principals towards counsellors based on gender?*

Table 3: Independent T test

Gender	N	Mean	SD	DF	Value	Sig
Male	22	28.36		2.78	44	0.498
Female	24	27.79	4.67			0.62145

NS= No. of Significant of alpha level of 0.05

Results in table 3 shows that the male principals do not perceive differently from the female principals about Guidance Counsellor in schools in Bayelsa State. That is $t(44) = 0.498, P > 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study revealed that principals agreed that they do not have a good knowledge of who a counsellor is and in his/her actual roles in the school setting. From the instrument given above it was x-rayed that out of the questions seven items (i.e. item number 3,4,5,6,7,8, & 10) showed that they agreed that they do not have a good perception of Guidance Counsellors. While item number 1,2,9) indicates that they have a good perception of the Guidance Counsellor. This may be a cover up in other to protect their office. From the research it has already been revealed that principals don't understand the role of a Guidance Counsellor, that is why they feel a Guidance Counsellor can perform any other role in the school, a Counsellor from their response can perform the role of a school disciplinary, take the place of an absent teacher, any other teacher can do the walk of a Guidance Counsellor. Arowolo (2013) also discovered that when Counsellors are posted to schools, Principals assign duties to them.

According to Ikejiaku and Torubeli (2010) a counsellor is not supposed to teach, nor to handle any other work like a school disciplinarian. The Counsellor's work is such a tedious one that demands great concentration and dedication. It involves rendering educational services, vocational services and personal social services to a school. The Counsellor also needs to source for information concerning his job, attend conferences and seminars and also conduct group and individuals counselling. Where will he/she in the midst of all these responsibilities be able to shoulder other responsibilities attached to his/her office? Worst still, from the research, it was revealed that they can be employed but there are no offices for them and that funding too is also a problem. Yusuf, Zahyah, Lasis, Adekola and Famola (2021) also asserted that schools do not have a good counselling unit. All these are not palatable for the Guidance Counsellor. At the end the Guidance Counsellor may be more frustrated and may decide to abandon Guidance and Counselling for the teaching job.

CONCLUSION

This paper examines the perception of Guidance Counsellors by Nigerian Secondary school principals. The issue of gender was also examined. The study revealed that the roles of Guidance Counsellor are not properly understood by principals.

However, concerning gender, the result shows that male principals do not perceive differently from the female principals about Guidance Counsellors in schools in Bayelsa state.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The Counselling association of Nigeria, Bayelsa state chapter should organize a forum with all principals in the state schools especially Bayelsa state and educate them on the importance of the profession and the need for their employment.
2. The Counselling Association of Nigeria should make their investigations on states that do have Guidance Counsellors in schools and enforce the federal government blue print on Guidance Counsellor on such states.
3. Guidance Counsellors when employed should not be lazy for people not to look down on the profession. He should handle all duties within his office with all seriousness.
4. The counsellor may be wrongly perceived by principals as a result of sheer ignorance. An awareness programme can be organized through the social print and electronic media, for the public, by the Government in line with the Federal Government's injunction on Guidance and Counselling.
5. Conferences, workshops and seminars can be organized to sensitize principals on the roles of the Guidance Counsellors.
6. The counsellor if employed, should make do with any available space and work with it in order to prove his/her worth.
7. As regards funding, the Counsellor can source for fund through non-governmental organizations, local government, parents-teachers association, oil companies etc. in order to ensure effectiveness in his/her job.

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